

Public Summary: D2.4 Microfluidic Assay for Detection of Glycosylated Non-Natural

Acceptors

Enzymes are essential for developing environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional petroleum-based chemicals used in consumer products like nutraceuticals, cosmetics, and detergents. However, discovering and engineering new enzymes can be time-consuming and expensive. As part of the RADICALZ project, INSAT partner is leveraging cutting-edge microfluidic technology to streamline the discovery of carbohydrate-active enzymes involved in the synthesis of consumer products.

In D2.4, microfluidics is utilized for the rapid identification of enzymes able to catalyze new glycosylation reactions. The process involves a fluorescence-based assay to track successful glycosylation events in tiny droplets at rates of millions of droplets per hour. This workflow could be applied to screen for glyco-enzymes from the natural diversity or that have been protein engineered to generate glyco-derivatives with enhanced solubility, stability, and/or biocompatibility. By optimizing this workflow, INSAT partner aims to facilitate the delivery of enzymes that enhance the sustainability and performance of a variety of novel bio-based consumer products of interest for cosmetic or nutraceutical applications.

Microfluidics droplets from the fluorescence-based assay